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Trend Of Voters Turnout In The 2023 general election In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Since the inception of Nigerian's fourth republic in 1999, voter's turnout in general elections has exhibited variations across different electoral cycles. The presidential, gubernatorial, and legislative elections held till date have all witnessed differing levels of voter participation in general elections. It was noted that Nigeria's diverse cultural, religious, and regional identities can shape voters turnout pattern. Ethnic and religious affiliations, combined with regional political interests, can influence voter's choices and their willingness to participate in elections. to understand the trends of voter turnout in general elections in Nigeria and how likely it was influenced by a complex interplay of socio-economic, political, and regional factors. Recognizing these underlying dynamics is vital for fostering a vibrant and participatory democracy that truly represents the will of the Nigerian people.

Keywords: 2023 general election;

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria, as Africa's populous country and a vibrant democracy, has experienced a series of general elections since the restoration of civilian rule in 1999. With the 2023 General Elections held on the 25th February and 11th March, 2023 for presidential, house of representative/senate and governorship/state house of assemblies respectively. One crucial aspect that has consistently drawn attention in the Nigerian electoral process is voter turnout-the proportion of eligible voters who participate in casting their ballots during election. Understanding the trends in voter turnout is imperative, as it does not only reflects the level of citizen's engagement but also significantly shapes the electoral outcomes and the country's political trajectory.

Since the inception of Nigeria's Fourth Republic in 1999, voter turnout in general elections has exhibited variations across different doctoral cycles. The presidential, gubernatorial, and legislative election held in 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011 and 2015 has all witnessed differing levels of voter participation (Adetula et al, 2018) including 2019 and 2023 general elections. These fluctuations have been attributed to diverse factors that intersect with the socio-political dynamics of the country.

Nigeria's socio-economic landscape plays a crucial role in determining voter turnout. Income inequality, poverty levels, and unemployment rates have been associated with varying degrees of political apathy or enthusiasm among citizens (Omotola, 2017). Moreover, accessibility to polling stations and transportation challenges in remote areas can also influence voter participation, particularly in regions with inadequate infrastructure. We cannot overlook the introduction of new technologies such as Bimodal Voter

Accreditation System (BVAS) and the IREV portal for real time voting update that could pose a series of challenges to both INEC staff and electorate who are illiterate and find it difficult to operate.

Political awareness and efficacy among citizens influence their willingness to participate in the electoral process. Factors such as trust in the electoral system, belief in the effectiveness of voting, and a sense of civic responsibility can impact voter turnout (Omotola, 2017). Perceptions of electoral malpractices, rigging, or voter intimidation can dampen citizens' confidence in the fairness of the process and deter them from casting their votes (Adebanwi, 2018).

Nigeria's diverse cultural, religious, and regional identities can also shape voter turnout patterns. Ethnic and religious affiliations, combined with regional political interests, can influence voter's choices and their willingness to participate in elections (Adetula et al, 2018). Political mobilization efforts by candidates and parties may also vary in effectiveness across different regions, affecting voter engagement. The 2023 General Elections was fiercely contested, understanding the dynamics influencing voter turnout is more crucial than ever. Policymakers, election officials, political parties, and civil society organizations need to develop evidence-based strategies to enhance voter engagement and promote a more inclusive democratic process.

To understand the trends of voter turnout in the 2023 General Elections in Nigeria and how likely it was influenced by a complex interplay of socio-economic, political, and regional factors. Recognizing these underlying dynamics is vital for fostering a vibrant and participatory democracy that truly represents the will of the Nigerian people.

Statement of the Problem

Despite being an emerging democracy with series of successful electoral cycles since 1999, Nigeria continues to grapple with the challenge of low voter turnout in its general elections. The trend of voter turnout in the 2023 General Elections is critical in understanding the extent to which Nigeria has succeeded in addressing this challenge. Many Nigerians continue to experience inadequate public services, unreliable infrastructure and irrational governmental policies which according to Omodia (2012) constitute a cause to low voters turnout. This has undermined the quality of elections held in Nigeria in the various electoral circles. The 2023 general elections saw no difference as there appear to be issues that must have propelled or caused a low voters turnout and in turn this low voter turnout has had a large impact on Nigerian elections. Thus, understanding the impact of low voter turnout in the 2023 general election is crucial. As it will give insight into the dynamics that impacts citizen's willingness to engage in the electoral process and the reasons for such level of engagement or participation in the electoral processes.

In the light of the problem of low voter turnout in Nigeria, a key aspect that constitutes such problem is the political awareness and voters education as the disposal of citizens prior to general elections. It is important to note that the role of political awareness and voter education of citizens participation in 2023 general election was a major problem to our electoral circle, as most persons or citizens have little or inadequate political education and awareness as to drive them to participate in the 2023 general election. The unwillingness of voters in carrying out their civic responsibility amid their concern for a more transparent process in determining the political outcomes and democracy of Nigeria in the 2023 general election is keen to the ensuing problems of this research.

Concept of Election

Election, no doubt, is one of the defining features of representative democracy. Its concrete way for citizens who are within the voting age in a country to exercise their franchise in determining who rules them. Casting of votes during election is a powerful weapon to either select those contestants adjudicated to have good tract records or vote out those leaders who fail to fulfill their campaign promises. However, Dye et al (2009), defined election as a major mechanism for the enrollment of political leadership in democratic societies, it is the key to effective participation in a democratic dispensation and the means through which people give their consent to democratic dispensation and the means through which people give their consent to government. Roger (1982), sees election as the route through which electorates

choose by voting officers either to act on their behalf or to represent them in an assembly with a view to leading or administration. According to Heywood (2006), election is a device for filling an office or positions through choices made by a designated body of people called electorates. Election simply means the process through which eligible electorates casts their votes in order to select from among political contestants that vie for various elective positions for the purpose of quality leadership, quality representation and good governance.

Concept of Voting

Voting is one of the cardinal principles of the democratic system of government and the importance of political and election participations in democratic societies have increased dramatically. This brings us to a sharper definition of voting; therefore, voting in this capacity refers to aggregating individual preferences into a collective decision in an election, the action of formally indicating one's choice of candidates or political party at an election (Gerber, Green & Shachar, 2023). Voting denotes the means whereby a number of persons are enabled to indicate two or more proposals or between two or more candidates for some offices. It is therefore a means of aggregating individual preference into a collective decision. The term generally refers to the process by which citizens choose candidates for public office or decide political questions submitted to them.

According to Bromhead (1960) as cited in Okolie (2004), voting denotes the means whereby a number of persons are enabled to indicate their agreement or disagreement with some propositions, or their preference as between two or more proposals or between or more candidates for some office. It is therefore a means of aggregating individual preference into collective decisions. As noted by Stokes (1963) cited in Okolie (2004), voting is not the sole means of aggregating individual preferences, other means include market mechanism and processes of informal interaction in many social and political groups.

Usually when a vote is taken the decision of the majority prevail; for some types of decisions, it may be provided that there must be an absolute majority of those qualified to vote, or some majority greater than half, either of all those qualified to vote or of all these actually voting, for a particular decision to be valid. A voice vote, in which the voters shout "yes or no", is simple and quick, but acceptable as a final decision only if those declared to be in minority are satisfied that they really are in a minority (Okolie, 2004). Voting in elections into public offices is usually conducted using ballot boxes. Voting therefore takes the form of thumb printing in the ballot paper provided. Voting processes have undergone transformations over the year in Nigeria, from secret ballot system; the electoral commission experimented with open-ballot system, and modified open-secret ballot system (Okolie, 2004). The voting system varies from country to country but one basic point that underlie all voting in a given socio-formation is decision making. To vote is to make a decision about a particular issues or issues at stake. However, the direction of the decision is determined by certain factors which shape voting behaviour.

Concept of Voting Behaviour and Political Apathy

Voting behaviour according Heywood, (2004) connotes a collection of attitudes, values and beliefs in which individuals of a given society have towards elections both at the local, national and international level. While Harrop and Miller in Heywood (2004) using a constructivist paradigm, explained voting behaviour as a pattern of political participation mostly taking place in democratic societies where people react to certain laid down values, principles and beliefs how they choose their leaders. These set of beliefs could be based on age, sex, ethnicity, religion and education. Voting behaviour is clearly shaped by short-term and long-term influences. Short-term influences are specific to a particular election and do not allow conclusion to be drawn about voting patterns in general. The chief short-term influence is the state of the economy, which reflects the fact that there is usually a link between government's popularity and economic variables such as unemployment, inflation and disposable income. Another short-term influence on voting is the personality and public standing of party leaders. This is particularly important, because media exposure portrays leaders as the brand image of their party (Heywood, 2004). In Nigeria, the voting behaviour has become constituted by a lack of interest in the political activities of the state by

citizens; this is due to irregularities in governance and the failure to keep to promises by political actors, which has led to political apathy.

Political apathy is “the lack of psychological involvement in public affairs, emotional detachment from civic obligations and abstention from political activity” (INEC and FES, 2011). It is part of the general decline in citizens’ involvement in political activities of a particular country or nation (Fagunwa, 2015). Citizens of a country may be active politically in opinion aggregation, policy formulation, civic engagement with government and political leaders in the attendance and participation in political functions and activities like seminars, summits, conferences, rallies, debates, town hall meetings, dialogues, political consultations, etc. and yet refused to turn out to vote on Election Day. This is why voter participation in the electoral process (voter turnout) helps in determining political apathy. The key concepts in the electoral process of electoral participation, especially in the sub-field of political apathy will be defined. Since election is the official act or process by which citizens of a democracy choose their representatives for public or political offices. When a candidate who presents himself or herself in an election is elected, citizens who are also called the electorate (those registered to voting in an election), expect political accountability from their political representatives with the exercise of their mandates. When this is not the case according to Ebenezer (2017), “voter apathy ensures which results in low voter turnout” during elections.

Voter Turnout: Voter turnout is simply the percentage of eligible voters who cast their ballots in an election. Pintor and Sullivan (2010) argued that voter turnout is usually expressed in the percentage of voters who cast a vote. This includes those who cast blank and invalid votes in an election. Geys (2006) insisted that “it is the total number of people who vote in a given election, usually given as a percentage”. The level of political participation throughout voter turnout, according to Ebenezer (2017) “determines the respect or disrespect such government gets from the people”. However, political apathy can be adequately measured in a democracy, during an election

Democracy: Democracy is defined by Dunn (2005) as “self-government, a way of living together in political freedom which enabled the characters and refined the sensibilities of an entire community. It is a society government itself where citizens choose freely and immediately from themselves”. This is in line with Abraham Lincoln’s definition that democracy implies “government of the people by the people, for the people. The requirement for democracy is people’s consent. This consent is supposedly given through elections and voter turnout. Lack of voter turnout, or the exercise of political apathy, is seen, in most cases, as lack of consent in a democratic or political system.

Political Participation: This is defined as the willingness, activeness and full involvement of citizens in the political and electoral processes, especially voting during an election. Political or electoral participation in an election accord legitimacy to a political system with the authority or mandate to act or take policy actions or decisions on behalf of the entire citizens. The concept of political apathy therefore requires a comprehensive understanding of the intricacies of political, governance and inclusiveness in a particular political system.

Disenchantments, indifferences or discontent for or against an electoral or political system could result in political apathy. This determines political apathy using the demography of political participation in election in Nigeria in 2023.

Trend of Voter Turnout in Nigeria 2023 General Election

According to obtainable information in INCE data base, there are 18 registered political parties that participated in the 2023 general election, with 15,331 contestants from various political parties for various political positions ranging from that of the President, to that of the State House of Assembly. The total number of registered voters amounted to 93,469,008 voters in the entire federation of 774 local government areas. The total number of registration areas/wards amounts to 8,809,000 with 176,846 polling units across the country. Of the 93.4 million registered voters this year, 87.2million people collected their Permanent Voters Card while 6,229 did not collect their voters card and the total number of actual voters on election day was only 24.9 million (INEC, 2023). Nigerians’ aversion to voting during

elections is well documented, but the challenge saw a new low during the 2023 general elections, when citizens went out to elect federal lawmakers and the president in an exercise that was keenly watched across the world.

Since its return to democratic rule in 1999, Nigeria has enjoyed uninterrupted democracy, the first such lengthy period since the country's independence in 1960. Up to 93 million people in Africa's most populous country and biggest economy registered to vote ahead of the 2023 elections. It was the first leg of the seventh general election since the end of military rule in 1999 (Premium Times, 2023).

In the build-up to the elections, a combination of a severe cash crunch as well as a protracted scarcity of petrol, ensured Nigerians, particularly the youth, picked a strong interest in participating in the 2023 election. But, the voter turnout was abysmal, the lowest since Nigeria's independence. In 36 states, less than half of the eligible population turned out to vote, and no state had a turnout above 40 percent. In the three largest states based on voter registration – Lagos, Kano and Rivers – less than a third of the eligible population voted. Rivers turnout was a shameful 15.6 percent, the lowest in the country, despite producing a lot more votes in past elections.

Overall, the national turnout was 29 percent, no election had a lower participation rate in the six decades of Nigeria's independence. Of the 93.4 million registered voters this year, 87.2 million people collected their Permanent Voter Card and the total number of actual voters on election day was only 24.9 million. Barely 9 million people voted for the President Bola Ahmed Tinubu who will now govern over 200 million Nigerians. Since 2011, the turnout of voters has seen a steady decline (Kabir, 2023).

Before 2023, the 2019 election recorded the lowest voter turnout of 34.75 percent. In 2019, only a meagre 28.6 million votes were cast despite 82 million eligible voters. The winner, President Muhammadu, Buhari, was re-elected with just over 15 million votes in a country of more than 200 million citizens. More than half of the country's population is within the voting age range (Kabir, 2023). The 2019 rate was the lowest of all recent elections held on the African continent. Data compiled by the International Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance (I-IDEA), an intergovernmental organization that supports sustainable democracy worldwide, reveals that the turnout of voters in that election was the second lowest in the history of elections held in African countries, and it was only slightly better than the 32.3 percent recorded in the 1996 Zimbabwean presidential election (I-IDEA, 2023). This means that Nigeria's 2023 presidential election has the worst turnout in Africa.

Several factors have been given for the low voter turnout in Nigerian elections. These include voter apathy and poor economic situation. Premium Times a reputable news agency in Nigeria also reported how the electoral commission, INEC, contributed to the low voter turnout in the recent election through its late deployment of officials and materials to polling units. Overall, voter apathy is a major challenge in Nigeria's democracy. There is a worrying trend of public disinterest in or indifference towards the electoral and democratic processes. Commenting on the development, Idayat Hassan, the director of the Centre for Democracy and Development (CCD) said the low participation might be due to the failure of democracy to deliver development. "The failure of democracy to deliver development has made many to not have interest in participating in elections," she said, adding "violence and voter suppression also played a huge role in diminishing voter turnout."

In 1999, turnout was 52.3 percent. Officially, it grew to 69 percent in 2003, and it has fallen since then, first to 57.5 percent in 2007, then to 53.7 percent in 2011, before dropping to 43.7 percent in 2015 and finally dropping to 29% in 2023 general election (INEC, 2023). In the 1999 election, 30.2 million people out of the 57.9 million registered citizens actually voted. Both the number of registered voters and the number of votes cast increased in the following election in 2003, with 42 million out of 60.8 million registered Nigerians voting (69 percent voter turnout). The 2003 election still has the highest rate of participation since the end of military rule in 1999.

By 2007, despite an increase in the number registered voters to 61.5 million, the total votes cast significantly dropped to 35.3 million (57.5 percent voter turnout). Registered voters and total votes further increased to 73.5 and 39.4 respectively in 2011. Then the numbers dropped to 75.4 million and 29.4 million 2015 (INEC, 2023). These figures put Nigeria among the 10 countries with the lowest voter

turnout in the world. Rwanda recorded a 98.15 percent voter turnout in 2017, the highest in the world so far.

“These dwindling numbers highlight how Nigeria’s politics and state institutions continue to exclude rather than include,” said Leena Hoffmann, an associate fellow of the Africa Programme at Chatham House London. Ms Hassan of CDD called on INEC to improve its election management and embark on a voter register audit. “Nigeria doesn’t have a voter register audit, an audit that takes out those who have died and all other ineligible voters from the system.”

“The fact that a significant percentage of Nigerians fail to engage in elections is a concern and perhaps points to growing disillusionment with their ability to shape a more democratic society,” she said. Nigeria held its governorship election on 18 March 2023 and would subsequently do so far out circle states of Bayelsa, imo and Kogi gubernatorial election in 11th November, 2023 (INEC, 2023).

Turnout in gubernatorial elections varies across Nigerian state. Data from the 2019 gubernatorial election show that many states recorded low voter turnout in their elections. Turnout rates varied from above 50 percent in Borno, Jigawa, Katsina and Taraba to a worrying low of 18 percent in Lagos State, the country’s most cosmopolitan city

Only a few elections had higher percentages. Some recent by-elections recorded as low as 3 and 8 percent voter turnout. Only 10 percent of eligible voters voted for Governor Charles Soludo of Anambra in 2021 gubernatorial election (Kabir, 2023).

Causes of Low Voters Turnout in 2023 General Election in Nigeria

Omodia (2012) opined that political poverty exists based on the exclusion of an individual or group from political participation. That is, politically an individual or group could be said to be poor based on their exclusion from participation in the political process. Causes of low voters turnout are as follows:

Insecurity

Insecurity played a pivotal role in depressing voter turnout during the 2023 general election in Nigeria. The country has grappled with a multitude of security challenges, most notably the persistent Boko Haram insurgency in the northeast, which has instilled a deep sense of fear and instability among the populace. Frequent attacks on civilians, including during past elections, have made many Nigerians wary of venturing to polling stations, as they fear becoming targets of violence or abduction. Additionally, ethnic and religious conflicts in various regions have further exacerbated insecurity, with the potential for clashes between rival groups deterring citizens from participation in the electoral process. Political thuggery, intimidation, and inadequate security measures have only intensified these fears, resulting in low voter turnout and a compromised democratic process.

Furthermore, the insecurity-induced low voter turnout not only poses a significant challenge to the legitimacy of Nigeria’s democracy institution but also perpetuates a cycle of political disenfranchisement. When a substantial portion of the population abstains from voting due to security concerns, the resulting election officials may not truly represent the diverse interests and voices of the nation. This can lead to a further erosion of trust in the government and elected representative, as citizens perceive their concerns and safety as secondary to the political elite’s interests. Ultimately, this disillusionment with the political process can breed cynicism and disengagement, creating a vicious cycle where low voter turnout and insecurity reinforce each other.

Political Apathy

Political apathy is a deeply rooted issue contributing to low voter turnout in general elections in Nigeria. One of the primary drivers of this apathy is the widespread distrust in political institutions. Nigeria has a history marred by corruption scandals, electoral fraud, and the mismanagement of public resources. Such systemic issues have eroded the faith of many citizens in the integrity of their government and the electoral process. When people believe that their votes will not result in meaningful change or that politicians are primarily driven by self interest, they often choose to abstain from voting as an act of protest or due to sheer disillusionment.

Additionally, the perceived ineffectiveness of voting is a significant deterrent to political engagement. Despite participating in elections, many Nigerians continue to experience inadequate public services, unreliable infrastructure, and limited economic opportunities. This disillusionment leads to the belief that elections have little impact on improving their daily lives, further fueling political apathy. The failure of elected officials to deliver on their promises exacerbates this sentiment.

Institutional Arrangement

In the Nigerian state, the democratic process of governance and political participation is seen as a learning one. This is because the democratic structures and institutions are very fragile and coupled with the fact that the citizenry to a great extent manifest low level of democratic culture as a result of long years of military dictatorship and the fragile and weak nature of political institutions in Nigeria such as political parties, civil society organizations, mass media and even government agencies such as the National Orientation Agency, Electoral Body (INEC) that are charged with the responsibility of holding elections, creating political awareness and political education.

Thus, the democratic process is associated with low level of voter cum political education, party indiscipline on the part of party officials and party representatives in government, vote manipulations and political representation that is not people centered, and weak party opposition among others.

Political Culture and Socialization

Osuji (2005) notes that Nigeria has multi-political culture as a result of the heterogeneous, numerous divergent ethnic and religious groups that exist in the country, each with its own political culture due to their historical and political development and it would take over a thousand years of common experience for the disparate groups in Nigeria to develop a unified perception of phenomena and unified political culture that would eventually blend into democracy as a system which explains many reasons as to why people find it hard to differentiate between ethnic/religious domain and political domain which would automatically define their commitment to political participation or apathy.

Political Education

As regard political education, the fragile and weak nature of political institutions in Nigeria, especially political parties, sensitization groups like the NOA, media, COSs has led to a scenario in which voting is not based on issues or ideologies. This is coupled with the fact that, political parties in opposition do not present themselves as credible alternatives to the party in government, the effect therefore is that the electorate in most cases do not tend to make informed decisions on what the parties stand for and how their programmes are likely going to affect them. This is in addition to the fact that vote cancellation is still on the high side and voter turn-out is on the low and this cannot be divorced from political education (Omodia, 2012). According to Jim Una, "A failure to vote for a candidate is a ballot cast for the opponent of the candidate", thus re-emphasizing the role citizens play during elections and also the link between political participation and voter's turnout. There is generally positive relationship between political information and citizen participation in campaigns, a generally negative relationship between information and number of floating voters. Moreover, given that political and civic activists tend to be better informed than voters in Nigeria, activists can and influence voters from one election to the other, even though it is not clear whether change among activists can also translate into change among voters.

CONCLUSION

Insecurity played a vital role in causing low voter's turnout during the 2011 general election in AMAC simply out of the fear of terrorist acts like bombing as witnessed in the bombing of an INEC Headquarters in Suleja, Abuja that caused much fear among electorates who resolved to stay at home than risk their lives in voting with no guarantee that their mandate would be protected by the electoral body or would be leaders causing low voters' turnout.

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